

CURRICULUM VITAE

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name Covaci (Sterpu) S. Brîndușa
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 Sex Feminine
 Occupational field Research, Education

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

- Period April 2022 – present
- Occupation or position held President – Rector, Professor, Ph.D. coordinator
- Main activities and responsibilities University management, Teaching
- Name and address of employer CBM International University USA
- Type of business or sector Education, Research, Management
- Period July 2020 – present
- Occupation or position held Senior Researcher
- Main activities and responsibilities Research and teaching in Economy (Management, Entrepreneurship, Marketing, Accounting, Finance, Commerce, Business and Agri-Business, Informatics) and in Agronomy (Agriculture, Mountain Economy)
- Name and address of employer Centre for Mountain Economy – Romanian Academy
- Type of business or sector Research, development, innovation and education
- Period July 2020 – present
- Occupation or position held Senior Researcher, Tutor/Instructor & Director
- Main activities and responsibilities Research and teaching in Economy (Management, Entrepreneurship, Marketing, Accounting, Finance, Commerce, Business and Agri-Business, Informatics) and in Agronomy (Agriculture, Mountain Economy)
- Name and address of employer Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom
- Type of business or sector Research, development, innovation and education
- Period October 2019 – present
- Occupation or position held Parenting & Preschooler Educator (Online schooling)
- Main activities and responsibilities Preschooler - Milestones development (Physical, Cognitive, Linguistic, Social & Emotional), Montessori activities, Structural activities (according to Romanian National Curriculum & Kinedu Company development & learning plans for 2-7 years old)
- Name and address of employer Kinedu Company, Monterrey Nuevo León – Mexico (New York - USA & Sao Paolo – Brazil, secondary activity points)
- Type of business or sector E-learning
- Period October 2015 – 2020
- Occupation or position held Associate Professor, PhD (October 2015), Vice-Rector (April 2016), Senior researcher II (November 2017)
- Main activities and responsibilities Teaching courses and seminars, research
- Name and address of employer Adventus University, Romania
- Type of business or sector Didactic, research and management
- Period August 2014 – June 2020
- Occupation or position held Senior Researcher
- Main activities and responsibilities Research and tutoring
- Name and address of employer Institute for World Economy – Romanian Academy
- Type of business or sector Research-development- innovation-tutoring
- Period April 2014 – October 2015
- Occupation or position held Tutor in social sciences and humanity / start-ups, Teaching project management
- Main activities and responsibilities Research, innovation and teaching – coordination of a group formed by 24 PhD students and postdoctoral fellows in order to realize their PhD and postdoctoral researches and teaching project management for 255 PhD students and postdoctoral fellows; Project: Horizon 2020 doctoral and postdoctoral studies: promoting the national interest through excellence, competitiveness and responsibility in Romanian fundamental and applied scientific research
- Name and address of employer Institute for World Economy – Romanian Academy
- Type of business or sector Research-development- innovation and teaching
- Period February 2011 – June 2016
- Function or occupied post President
- Activities and responsibilities Research-development-innovation-tutoring activities
- Name and address of the employer Osterreichish-Rumanischer Akademischer Verein, Austria
- Activity type and sector Research-development-innovation activity
- Period October 2011 – September 2012
- Function or occupied post University lecturer, associate, Project manager
- Activities and responsibilities Didactic activity – Microeconomic, Enterprise economy, Business administration I, Business administration II, Entrepreneurship; Project management activity
- Name and address of the employer Titu Maiorescu University, Romania
- Activity type and sector Didactic and management activity
- Period August 2010 – present
- Function or occupied post Director, Researcher, Tutor/Instructor
- Activities and responsibilities Research in economy, 3 research projects
- Name and address of the employer Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences, Austria & United Kingdom
- Activity type and sector Coordination and research in economy
- Period February 2009 – present
- Function or occupied post Project manager - coordinator (PMC), project member (PM)
- Activities and responsibilities ESEN - Fundamental programme of the Romanian Academy CFMR (PM), "Practical students - active and integrated students" SHU (PMC), "ProFeminAntrep - Promoting equal opportunities in entrepreneurship" SHU (PMC), "European

quality in higher education" SHU (PM), "Doctoral scholarship in order to sustain doctoral research activities in technical and humanity area, for environment protection and sanity, of national, European and world legislation with eco-economic and socio-economic impact CERDOCT" UNIVNT (PM), "Doctoral scholarship of eco-economic and bio-economic complex learning in order to sustain safety and security food from anthropic ecosystems" (PM) RA-NIER, "New work places in rural area: Romania – Austria and Opportunities for quick integration of unemployed from West and Centre of Romania" (PMC) ORAV, "Juridical studies – between theory and practice" (PMC) AICU-RNI, "Chance to education, your chance!" (PMC) BCM

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>Centre for Financial and Monetary Research (CFMR) & National Institute for Economic Research – Romanian Academy (RA-NIER), Spiru Haret University (SHU), Alexandru Ioan Cuza University - Romanian Notarial Institute (AICU-RNI), Nicolae Titulescu University (UNIVNT), Osterreichish-Rumanischer Akademischer Verein (ORAV), Bethlem Church Medgidia (BCM)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector • Period • Function or occupied post • Activities and responsibilities 	<p>Development & research projects October 2008 – present Senior Researcher Research in economy, 2 research projects</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>Advancement of Scholarly Research Centre, New York, United States of America</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector • Period • Function or occupied post • Activities and responsibilities 	<p>Research in economy October 2007 – September 2014 Assistant professor/University lecturer, Director Research Centre</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>Didactic activity – Credit and banking, Monetary and financial economy, Money and monetary policies, Risk economy, Econometric and economic forecasting, Economic efficiency, Statistic, Financial policies and institutions, Financial enterprise management</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector • Period • Function or occupied post • Activities and responsibilities 	<p>Spiru Haret University, Romania Didactic activity October 2002 – November 2009 Educational Director, Projects member</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>Leonardo da Vinci, Comenius - Youth Europe Dr. I. C. Cantacuzino College, Romania</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector • Period • Function or occupied post • Activities and responsibilities 	<p>External funds projects October 2000 – August 2007 Professor</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>Didactic and research for economic and informatics disciplines, Executive Director Virgil Madgearu Economical College, Industrial Electronics College, Dr. I. C. Cantacuzino College and Ecoprof College</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector • Period • Function or occupied post • Activities and responsibilities 	<p>Education and research October 2000 – August 2007 Project member</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>MESE, GLOBE, CAPS - Junior Achievement Romania and Young Enterprises Europe</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector • Period • Function or occupied post • Activities and responsibilities 	<p>Industrial Electronic College External funds projects October 1997 – September 2007, September 2012 – December 2014</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the employer 	<p>Director for marketing, Consultant marketing / Financial counselling Consulting in economy, marketing, PR</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity type and sector 	<p>SC Amway Marketing Romania SRL / SC Dana'S SRL / AIG Life Romania / Raiffeisen Banca pentru Locuinte Consulting</p>
EDUCATION AND TUTORING	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Period • Qualification / diploma • Disciplines studied / professional competencies • Name and institution type 	<p>1 October 2020 – 1 September 2023 PhD diploma Agronomy, Agriculture, Mountain Economy</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level in national or international classification 	<p>Oradea University, Romania PhD diploma, Level 6 November 2021</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Period • Qualification / diploma • Disciplines studied / professional competencies • Name and institution type 	<p>Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages / Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TESOL/TEFL) - Graduate certificate English Teaching, English Pedagogy</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level in national or international classification 	<p>World TESOL Academy, United Kingdom Continuing education November 2021</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualification / diploma • Disciplines studied / professional competencies • Name and institution type 	<p>Tutor/Instructor/Trainer - Graduate certificate Teaching, Instructor, Training, Adult education</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level in national or international classification 	<p>Teaching & Training Center, Romania Continuing education October 2021</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualification / diploma • Disciplines studied / professional competencies • Name and institution type 	<p>Specialized educator Graduate certificate Teaching, Pedagogy, Children education, Social work support, Caregiving</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level in national or international classification 	<p>Saint Giovanni Bosco Foundation, Romania Continuing education September 2020</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualification / diploma • Disciplines studied / professional competencies • Name and institution type 	<p>English language certificate, Advanced level English language</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level in national or international classification 	<p>Transylvania University of Brasov, Romania Continuous education 1 March 2013 – 30 May 2014</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualification / diploma • Disciplines studied / professional competencies • Name and institution type 	<p>Postdoctoral diploma Eco-economy, Bio-economy, Banca electronica, Eco-banking, Bio-banking, Financial and cybernetic security</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level in national or international classification 	<p>Romanian Academy – National Institute for Economic Research, Romania Postdoctoral researcher</p>

- In 2002-2007 period, at Ecoprof College I have been Didactic Chief and Responsible for Curricula, proposing new disciplines, new studies programmes and modification of the standardization area
- I have abilities in coordination and management, and I am doing volunteering (Pro-Life Foundation, International Children Care, Rise and Walk Association)

FOREIGN LANGUAGES

English (Duolingo Certificate 110), Italian (well), French (well)

SOCIAL SKILLS AND ABILITIES

I have competencies in working with a multitude of people, in different areas

ORGANIZATIONAL SKILLS AND ABILITIES

- Organising teams; - Organizing events, workshops, conferences; - Writing and implementing projects: national funds, European and international (CSA USA; Romanian Academy/INCE, ARACIS, UTM, ORAV Austria, Zealandina Ag UK)

COMPUTER SKILLS AND ABILITIES

Utilizer: Windows, Linux, Microsoft Office, Acrobat Reader, Autocad, LabView, HTML, SPSS
Programmer: Pascal, C/C++, Java, FoxPro, SQL

03/06/2025